

A Rare Case of Quadruple Nuchal Cord Strangulation Resulting in Intrauterine Fetal Demise: A Case Report

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Abstract

Background: Intrauterine fetal death (IUFD) remains a significant obstetric complication. While most cases are multifactorial, umbilical cord accidents—including nuchal cords—are silent contributors and often evade prenatal diagnosis. We report a case of an unbooked 32-year-old primigravida who presented at 39 weeks and 4 days of gestation age with an ultrasound report of intrauterine fetal death. The general examination revealed a height of 1.46m and a weight of 62kg. Other parameters were within normal limits. An abdominal examination revealed a singleton fetus in oblique cephalic lie, and symphysio-fundal height of 37cm. There was no palpable contraction, and fetal heart activity was not heard using Pinnard's stethoscope and by performing bedside ultrasound. A clinical pelvimetry was done and adjudged as a contracted pelvis. The couple was counseled on a caesarean section due to the contracted pelvis and oblique lie, which they consented to. Intraoperatively, a tight quadruple-loop of nuchal cord was found, with visible strangulation signs and no other fetal anomalies. The fresh stillborn female infant weighed 2.6 kg. The mother recovered smoothly, and the post-operative period was uneventful. The couple was provided with bereavement counseling. **Conclusion:** This case highlights the unpredictable and catastrophic potential of nuchal cords and emphasizes the need for heightened clinical suspicion and perinatal surveillance in late-term pregnancies.

Introduction

Intrauterine fetal death (IUFD) remains a significant obstetric complication. While most cases are multifactorial, umbilical cord accidents—including nuchal cords—are silent contributors and often evade prenatal diagnosis. A cord around the neck during pregnancy, known as a nuchal cord, is primarily caused by the baby's random movements within the womb. Other contributing factors can include an extra-long umbilical cord, an excess of amniotic fluid, which allows for more movement, and multiple gestation. A nuchal cord is a common finding in-utero and often minor. Tight nuchal cords, especially multiple loops, though rare, can compromise fetal circulation and

oxygenation, leading to fetal distress during labour and, in rare cases, a stillbirth [1-4].

The reported incidence of nuchal cord varies, with the highest rates of 43% in the 13th to 16th gestational week and 8.3% at birth [3,4].

Umbilical cord abnormalities, mainly umbilical cord constriction and coiling, are implicated in 11% of intrauterine fetal deaths within 16 weeks of gestational age. (4). Fetal demise due to nuchal cord entanglement has been reported to occur in the first or second trimester in two case reports [5,6].

Umbilical cord accidents—particularly nuchal cords—have been implicated in up to 20% of unexplained

More Information

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stillbirths [7]. A nuchal cord refers to one or more loops of the umbilical cord wrapped around the fetal neck [7]. Despite advances in prenatal imaging, many cord abnormalities remain undiagnosed until delivery. This case report presents a case of IUFD secondary to a quadruple-loop tight nuchal cord diagnosed incidentally during cesarean section.

Case Presentation

Mrs. K.D. was an unbooked 32-year-old primigravida at 39 weeks and 4 days of gestational age who complained of reduced perception of fetal movements of 2 days duration. Her antenatal booking was at a primary health care centre (PHC), and the care was uneventful. She had no medical comorbidity. There was no history of abdominal trauma or vaginal bleeding. Her blood group was O Rhesus positive, genotype AA, and there was no known allergies. She was using only the routine haematinics; she was not on any other medication. An ultrasound scan from a referring facility diagnosed IUFD, though it could not report the loops of the tight nuchal cord.

On examination, she was a young woman, afebrile, not pale, her height was 1.46m, and her weight was 62kg. An abdominal examination revealed a singleton fetus in oblique cephalic lie, symphysio-fundal height was 37cm, and compatible with her gestational age; the fetal head was 5/5th palpable and tilted towards RIF. There was no palpable contraction, and FHR was not heard using Pinnard's stethoscope. A clinical pelvimetry was done with an easily reached sacral promontory; the ischial spines were prominent, but the intertuberous diameters accommodated 4 knuckles and was adjudged as a contracted pelvis. A repeat scan at our hospital confirmed the absence of fetal cardiac activity. She was counseled for a Caesarean section mainly due to the finding of a contracted pelvis and oblique lie.

Figure 1: The Newborn with Four Loops of Umbilical Cord around the Neck

Intraoperative Findings included: a clean pelvis, well-formed lower uterine segment, a fresh stillborn female

with four tight loops of umbilical cord around her neck with deep neck indentation and petechiae haemorrhage, suggesting cord strangulation. There was fresh meconium-stained liquor, but the placenta appeared normal with no visible infarcts, abruption, or abnormal length. The fetus had no evidence of life, no visible congenital anomaly, and it weighed 2.6kg. The estimated blood loss was 500mls. The procedure was well tolerated.

The post-operative period was uneventful. She received intravenous antibiotics and analgesia. Postoperative counseling included a thorough explanation of the possible cause of fetal demise, grief support, and bereavement counseling. The couple was educated on the significance of the findings of a contracted pelvis, the need for an adequate inter-pregnancy interval, repeat caesarean section, and multidisciplinary expert care in subsequent pregnancies. She was also educated on breast care to prevent breast engorgement, which may result in an abscess if infected. She was followed up at the outpatient clinic following discharge from the hospital.

Discussion

Nuchal cords are common findings in term deliveries, present in up to 20-30% of births [7]. However, the clinical impact largely depends on the number of loops, tightness, and associated fetal compromise. Multiple tight loops, as seen in this case, can lead to impaired venous return, hypoxia, and ultimately, fetal demise. Progressive cord compression first impedes umbilical venous return, causing fetal hypovolemia and acidemia; with sustained or severe compression, arterial inflow is compromised, leading to acute hypoxic-ischemic injury. Cord vulnerability is influenced by length, coiling, and Wharton's jelly integrity; excessively long cords and multiple entanglements amplify tensile forces around the neck [8]. Placental and cord pathology in lethal events often demonstrates segmental constriction, venous thrombosis, and fetal vascular malperfusion [9]. Prenatal ultrasonography, including color Doppler, can detect nuchal cords; however, sensitivity decreases with multiple loops or tightness. The skill level of the sonographer also contributes to the ultrasonographic diagnosis of this condition. In this case, despite routine antenatal care and late-term presentation, the complication went undetected, reinforcing the unpredictable nature of such events. The incidental finding of a quadruple nuchal cord with petechial hemorrhages and neck indentations supports cord compression as the likely mechanism of IUFD. While most nuchal cords do not cause adverse outcomes, this case illustrates the critical need for fetal surveillance in patients presenting with reduced fetal movements, especially near term. Presentation as IUFD made it

unnecessary to attempt CTG monitoring or perform a biophysical profiling of the fetus.

Conclusion

This case emphasizes the limitations of prenatal surveillance in detecting potentially fatal umbilical cord accidents. While most nuchal cords are minor, multiple tight loops can be lethal. Clinicians should maintain a high index of suspicion in cases of reduced maternal perception of fetal movement and ensure prompt evaluation and appropriate intervention. More research is needed to establish guidelines for managing suspected cord complications during late pregnancy.

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